

New European Bauhaus Academy

From forest to frame Unlearning energy and material cultures

1st New European Bauhaus Academy Conference

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Bauhaus Earth

Circular Bio-based Europe

Joint Undertaking

Co-funded by the European Union

TG1

Education, training and academia

Universities and higher education institutions

Vocational education centres and technical schools

Training providers, associations, chambers

TG3

Public bodies and policy makers

City and regional planners

National ministries and legislators

Funding agencies

TG2

Construction ecosystem, private sector

Developers and contractors

Planning, architecture, engineering, design

Bio-based materials industry

Industry associations, financial services

TG4

General public and civil society

Citizens

NGOs and civil society

Media

What do we do at Bauhaus Earth?

5 Fields of Expertise:

Our international team of over 50 experts from climate, forestry and geosciences, architecture, urban planning and governance develops research-backed solutions — integrating five fields of expertise:

Systems Research and Data Analytics

Bauhaus Earth conducts interdisciplinary research on the relationship between climate and the built environment. Central to our work is the integration of global systems research with regionally grounded applications.

With tools such as transformation studies, modelling and life cycle assessments, we analyse building materials, assess supply-and-demand chains at multiple scales, and explore strategies for the transformation of the building sector.

Presentation of the Global Study, Annual ReBuilt Conference, 2023. © Bauhaus Earth

Technical and Material Innovation

We develop and test construction applications based on natural materials as well as on re-usable by-products from construction, industry, and consumer waste.

Through hands-on experimentation, Bauhaus Earth aims to make regenerative design more accessible, adaptable, and scalable for building value chains.

Opening of the ProtoPotsdam © 414films, 2024

Demonstration Building, Potsdam

Demonstration and Application

Translating research into practice: our global demonstration projects explore how regenerative construction can be implemented across varying scales and geographic contexts.

These regionally attuned demonstrators, ranging from prototypes to pavilions, activate local transformation processes by embedding transdisciplinary research in real-world settings.

Policy and Action Advisory

Through policy dialogues, high-level roundtables, strategic partnerships, and national and international coalitions, Bauhaus Earth helps to embed regenerative principles into the legislative structures.

We analyse regulatory, institutional and policy frameworks from local to global levels to identify barriers and opportunities, and to give evidence-based recommendations. Our aim is to place regenerative transformation at the heart of global policy agendas and to support its implementation.

Reconstruction of the People and Planet Conference hosted by Bauhaus Earth and the Pontifical Academy of Sciences: with Ursula von der Leyen, Klara Geywitz, Joachim Schellhuber, Francesco Sgarbi, Lesley Lokko, Diébédo Francis Kéré, Achim von Braun, Andrea Gebhard, Bjørk Ingels, Philipp Misselwitz et al., Vatican, 2022.

Education and Learning

Bauhaus Earth fosters a dynamic ecosystem for collaborative learning and innovation by connecting networks of stakeholders.

We cultivate shared ideas and practical knowledge through inclusive learning formats that promote interdisciplinary and cross-regional exchange.

Our world stands at the threshold of a profound transformation: the impacts of climate change are reshaping life on our planet. The depletion of natural resources is affecting nearly every aspect of society.

In this context, the construction and real estate sectors play a critical role, as they are responsible for nearly 40% of global CO₂ emissions.

To build a sustainable future, these industries must undergo a fundamental transformation, embracing innovative solutions that reduce the environmental impact while ensuring resilience and longevity.

**THIS
IS
THE
MOMENT**

Drawing inspiration from the pioneering spirit of the historic Bauhaus, Bauhaus Earth rethinks and transforms the built environment: from the major source of carbon emissions into a major carbon sink – driving a shift toward a sustainable future.

VISION

We envision a future in which buildings, cities, and landscapes proactively contribute to climate restoration — creating a positive impact on our planet and all its inhabitants. We advocate for systemic change: the transition to bio- and geo-based materials, circular construction, the reuse of existing buildings, and the regeneration of biodiversity.

THE MOCK-UP CORNER, using regional and circular value chains, showcases possibilities for contemporary construction. A load-bearing wall made of unfired earth bricks from Berlin excavation material rests on reused concrete elements. A timber ceiling made of Brandenburg pine sits at full story height, filled with earth bricks, hemp-earth insulation, and topped with a wooden flooring. On the outside, a weatherproof and insulated shell of biobased materials protects the structure.

ProtoPotsdam: prototype & education space

— Compressed Earth Blocks — Regenerative Timber Roof
— Re-use Fired Brick Base — Round Timber Column

The research pavilion ProtoPotsdam, built from regional, nature-based, and reused materials, demonstrates new pathways for climate-positive construction.

ProtoPotsdam

In collaboration with research partners at TU Berlin, the Eberswalde University for Sustainable Development, and FH Potsdam, Bauhaus Erde investigated the potential of regional resources as a response to regional challenges.

A site-specific education programme, developed by Bauhaus Earth together with local partners, is intended to inspire both professional audiences and civil society:

- on-site and online
- podcast and films
- workshops and events
- for professionals and for general public

URBANE MINE

ProtoPotsdam ProtoDIY

Paludi-Day: MOOR is MORE

SITUATING. Understanding Space through Taste

THE WALL: Building with Hemp and Hemp-Based Materials

Don't Screw Me. Timber Joints Without Glue or Metal

ProtoDIY am
ProtoPotsdam

From Forest to Frame

Regenerative Constructions with Bio-Based Materials

The one-day seminar is intended for professionals from architecture, construction, and design; decision-makers in building and sustainability policy; as well as individuals with an interest in sustainable, bio-based, and regenerative constructions.

How are forests, construction, and climate interconnected? The seminar combines theory and practice of nature-based materials. The morning session focuses on the foundations of regenerative construction: what does bio-based construction mean in a global context? What role do wood, or clay play as load-bearing, and balancing building materials in the climate-neutral transformation of the construction industry?

From Forest to Frame

Regenerative Constructions with Bio-Based Materials

In the afternoon, the program moves on to practical work: in the workshop, participants work in groups to build wall segments from regional, renewable, materials.

Introduction to prototyping: Frame construction and infill with bio-based insulation materials

Theresa Zschäbitz and Patricia Jeglitsch (Bauhaus Earth):
Insight into ongoing research projects
-HLH living lab, Berlin-Weissensee
-K12 and bio-based insulation, cooperative housing in Berlin

Hands-on prototyping: two types of an partition walls,
and clay plastering

Conclusion

The prototypes in combination with the educational formats demonstrate how Bauhaus Earth transforms research into tangible, transferable knowledge. Prototypical structures function not only as experimental building systems but as learning environments that make regenerative construction principles visible, understandable, and replicable.

These formats emphasize the importance of taking into account regional conditions, material availability, and diverse professional contexts.

By linking material experimentation, design research, and hands-on training, Bauhaus Earth creates bridges between theory and practice. These formats enable diverse audiences to engage directly with bio-based materials, circular strategies, and climate-responsive construction methods.

